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Solving the problem of depressed areas through creation of a good-neighborhood environment (Patrushi village case)

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

The active development and growth of urban centres often lead to a decline in the popularity of nearby areas such as small towns and villages. These areas experience negative population dynamic, stagnate in development and become economically and socially depressed. In such cases, it is essential to engage with the territory proactively by designing and implementing revitalisation projects. This paper examines the case of Patrushi village (Sysertsky District, Sverdlovsk Oblast) as a means of addressing the issue of depressed territories. To objectively forecast the potential outcomes of the proposed project, a range of general scientific research methods were employed, including data synthesis, deduction, interpretation of scientific data, analogy, objective modelling, and comparative analysis.

The authors propose a comfort-class residential neighbourhood project, complete with essential infrastructure and amenities, aiming to revitalise a depressed area. The project emphasises the creation of a high-quality living environment that fosters comfortable interaction and a sense of community among residents. Potential synergies between this proposal and a previously implemented project in Patrushi village are also explored. The appeal of suburban housing in this location is enhanced by Patrushi's proximity to the major urban centre of Yekaterinburg, making it attractive to prospective residents.

The paper presents calculations of the project's commercial effectiveness indicators, demonstrating its feasibility and the potential for successful implementation.

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INTRODUCTION

In Russia, integrated development projects for depressed areas are successfully implemented, leading to the creation of residential complexes, neighbourhoods, and districts that attract not only new residents but also investments, including business ventures. Consequently, depressed areas receive an impetus for growth, establishing favourable conditions for further development [1].

This article presents a practical, development-focused project addressing the problem of depressed territories in small towns and villages. It involves constructing affordable and comfortable housing based on the concept of integrated territorial development in Patrushi village (Sverdlovsk Oblast), including adjacent public spaces, while considering both current and prospective urban planning contexts.

The proposed solutions are expected to create new job opportunities for local residents and provide a modern residential complex equipped with favourable infrastructure, developed according to principles of good neighbourliness. The previously implemented residential complex Chisty Prudy in Patrushi village, which successfully increased the population [2], serves as a strong foundation for anticipating an even greater population growth following the implementation of the authors' proposed project.

A larger-scale housing development in Patrushi has the potential to halt the degradation of this depressed area. The original design concept of the housing complex aims to integrate existing and planned developments into a cohesive whole. The project carefully considers all local characteristics, including residents' needs, infrastructure shortcomings, and other challenging factors.

The revitalisation project presented in this paper can also serve as a model framework for analysing and designing integrated development concepts for similar depressed areas.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of revitalising depressed areas is not new. For instance, in 1957, Miernyk, while studying problems related to depressed territories, noted that a most effective way to restore these areas to normal functioning is through creation of new jobs [3]. Later, in 1966, Parr highlighted the limitations of such areas for the relocation of industrial enterprises [4].

In Russian practice, integrated development projects for depressed areas have been implemented with considerable success. These projects often result in the creation of residential complexes, neighbourhoods, and districts that attract not only new residents but also investments, including business ventures. Consequently, depressed areas gain momentum for development, and favourable conditions for growth are established.

One notable example is the Koshelev Project in Samara Oblast. This project is distinguished by the creation of neighbourhoods with diverse architectural styles and varying numbers of storeys within a large district. It also incorporates all necessary infrastructure, including schools, kindergartens, development centres, a polyclinic, shops, and recreational and sports facilities. Its appeal to potential residents lies in the variety of neighbourhood styles and their unique planning structures [1].

Another successful project is Lesnaya Polyana in Kemerovo Oblast – in 2016, it won the Masterplan category at the national stage of the Prix d'Excellence Awards. This project features an environmentally clean location and was developed with full engineering and social infrastructure from the outset. Its planning structure is characterised by a single community centre, alternating medium- and low-density residential areas, and a network of open parks, squares, and courtyards, all while ensuring transport accessibility [5].

Patarchanov, who studied the socio-economic aspects of industrially depressed territories, observed that industrial restructuring processes lead not only to deindustrialization but also to population decline, partly due to migration to more developed regions [6]. As a result, industrial activities are increasingly relocated outside cities, freeing up urban territories for housing developments [7], trendy creative spaces [8], or religious sites [9].

Notably, signs of territorial depression can be found in very different types of areas: single-industry towns [10], large cities with millions of inhabitants [11], or neglected zones adjacent to major urban centres [12].

Aleksandrova and Aigina, analysing the experience of revitalising depressed areas, concluded that sustainable revitalisation of a depressed community is achievable through a broad range of social, educational, infrastructural, cultural, and other activities aiming to promote future sustainable development [13]. Regional development can be further stimulated by the active involvement of young people

in territorial branding [14], enhancing the competencies of graduates – especially those with notable educational and scientific achievements [15] – and by introducing open e-learning systems [16].

Kireyeva, Nurlanova, and Kredina, assessing the socio-economic conditions of depressed territories, noted that regional disparities pose a significant challenge for national development, as small settlements often lack resources [17]. They also highlighted that a comfortable urban environment reduces the risk of a territory descending into a depressed state [18].

However, despite these insights, a shortage remains of research specifically focused on evaluating the effectiveness of revitalisation projects in depressed areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To assess the potential for revitalising a depressed area, a land plot (hereinafter referred to as LP) located in the village of Patrushi, within the Sysert Urban District of Sverdlovsk Oblast, was selected for analysis. Patrushi is situated along the Aramilka River, approximately 10 km southeast of Yekaterinburg and in close proximity to the town of Aramil. The area benefits from good transport accessibility: the city centre of Yekaterinburg can be reached by private vehicle in about 40 minutes under normal traffic conditions. Public transport is available via 13 local and two long-distance bus routes, and taxi services operate within Patrushi. Additionally, a car-sharing service is accessible in nearby Aramil. The road infrastructure is well maintained, with an asphalted secondary road featuring appropriate signage and markings, commonly used by private vehicles. Nearby settlements – Aramil, Bolshoi Istok, and Borodulino – form a “micro-agglomeration” within the greater Yekaterinburg agglomeration.

Notably, both Patrushi and Aramil have experienced population growth in recent years, driven by the development of new housing projects such as the Chistye Prudy Residential Complex, which is supported by essential social infrastructure [19]. The land plot under consideration is located adjacent to Chistye Prudy, offering significant synergy potential for the implementation of a new development project. The success of Chistye Prudy demonstrated clear consumer interest in the area, confirming sustained demand for residential real estate. Further residential expansion is planned in the surrounding area.

The allocated plot for the integrated development project spans 643,000 square metres and presents several constraints, including an irregular shape and a third-party road traversing the site. The area currently contains various structures, such as farm buildings, garages, a warehouse, and a production facility. According to the public cadastral data, the land is presently zoned for agricultural use, which does not align with the intended residential function. Consequently, one of the initial tasks will be to reclassify the land for residential development.

The study area is characterised by predominantly low-rise, economy-class individual housing development (IHD). However, there is a notable shortage of educational infrastructure – specifically, schools and pre-school facilities do not meet the needs of the growing population. To address this, the proposed integrated development project includes the construction of a school and two kindergartens, in line with service area standards.

General scientific research methods were employed, including data synthesis, deduction, interpretation of scientific data, analogy, objective modelling, and comparative analysis, to ensure an objective forecast of the project's promising outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on an analysis of the immediate surroundings of the LP and the socio-economic conditions of the area, the authors propose the development of a comfort-class residential complex. The choice of this housing category is driven by the demonstrated demand for comfort-class housing in Patrushi village and nearby Aramil. This demand is influenced by the location – somewhat removed from the city centre – as well as the financial capabilities of the local population.

Business-class housing, by contrast, would not integrate harmoniously into the architectural context of the surrounding area, nor align with the preferences of the target demographic. The comfort-class concept emerges as a balanced and viable solution: it offers a higher standard of living than the current housing stock while remaining more affordable than business-class developments.

The project adopts a minimalist, Scandinavian architectural style which has become increasingly popular in recent years. It emphasises simplicity and functionality, with a focus on clean geometric lines, regular forms, large open spaces, monochromatic colour palettes, and light-toned finishes [20].

Large panoramic windows and integrated lighting solutions are characteristic of the style, serving both practical and aesthetic purposes by highlighting the architectural features of the buildings. In addition, the minimalist style evokes a sense of contemporary European comfort and practicality. The target audience for the project includes young families and individuals with above-average monthly incomes, typically owning at least one car per household, who seek a modern, comfortable living environment near the city but with strong transport connectivity.

The proposed residential estate will consist of standardised development blocks, each incorporating distinct architectural solutions. This approach aims to avoid visual monotony while increasing the likelihood of meeting the diverse preferences of prospective buyers. At the same time, standardised design elements will reduce overall project costs – including documentation, materials, and construction works.

The project includes a variety of building types: detached houses, townhouses, and low-rise multifamily buildings (up to three storeys). A degree of customisation is foreseen, allowing residents to make minor modifications to their façades – within limits that preserve the coherent visual identity of the neighbourhood.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed site layout. The development plan is zoned according to building height and residential function:

- **Yellow**, located along the southern boundary, designates the area for two-storey detached houses, which will harmonise with existing structures on the adjacent land.
- **Green**, along the northern boundary, indicates the location of the townhouses.
- **Blue**, on the western boundary, represents areas for three-storey apartment buildings, replacing the current development.
- **Grey**, along both the western and eastern boundaries, marks designated parking areas.
- **Orange** shows the placement of kindergartens.
- **Pink** denotes the location of the school.
- **Brown** represents areas reserved for utility and communication infrastructure.

Within the study area lies the *Oblkomunenergo* building (providing heating, power, and water supply). Although located outside the residential project area – on the eastern side within the planned parking zone, the structure may present a

visual and psychological barrier to comfortable living. While the building does not pose any environmental or safety hazards, its presence near residential buildings is suboptimal. To mitigate this, the project proposes visually and physically buffering the utility zone from the residential area using open parking spaces designed for residents and visitors.

Figure 1 Zoning of the area

To ensure a comfortable living environment and enhance the quality of the area, the project envisions pedestrian-only zones within the neighbourhood. These streets will host street-level retail, cafés, and leisure facilities, making them vibrant public spaces that attract residents, foster a sense of community, and generate employment opportunities. Pedestrianisation throughout the neighbourhood is a key design element, aiming to provide a safe and pleasant environment, particularly beneficial for families with children.

Security will be ensured through an access control system, complemented by full video surveillance to prevent potentially dangerous situations. The entire residential estate will be divided into three access zones:

- **Public Zone:** Accessible to all residents and visitors, allowing unrestricted movement throughout shared public spaces.
- **Restricted Access Zone:** Limited to residents of adjacent buildings or blocks and their guests. Access is controlled via key cards or intercom systems.
- **Gated Zone:** Reserved exclusively for residents of individual buildings. Access is controlled via key cards or intercom systems and includes stairwells and rooftops.

All rooftops of apartment buildings and townhouses are designed to be open to residents of the respective building. These will offer a secluded setting for leisure and social interaction, encouraging neighbourly connections in a safe, relaxed environment.

Neighbourhood yards and playgrounds will be equipped with modern, multi-functional safety equipment and shaded structures to protect children from excessive sun exposure. Small architectural elements such as benches and swings will be installed for parental relaxation. Cleanliness and sustainability will be prioritised through the placement of numerous waste bins, including containers for separate waste collection.

To minimise unauthorised parking, designated parking areas will be located at the boundaries of the neighbourhood. Access to courtyards will be closed to private vehicles in order to maintain a secure pedestrian environment. Free, accessible parking is essential, as many residents may not be able to afford a private parking space at the time of property purchase. A lack of designated parking space often leads to spontaneous and unsafe vehicle placement, obstructing driveways and creating hazards for both pedestrians and drivers.

Given the site's distance from the city and the limited availability of public transport – only two intercity bus routes within walking distance, many residents will rely on personal vehicles. The availability of free, convenient parking is therefore expected to be a significant factor in attracting potential buyers.

A key distinguishing feature of the proposed residential complex will be the intentional creation of a strong neighbourhood environment, aiming to enhance the comfort and quality of life for residents. This environment will include landscaped areas, accessible rooftop spaces, zones for active recreation, sports courts, enclosed playgrounds, designated and informal parking areas, and pedestrian streets with retail and leisure amenities.

Each block within the complex will include **several distinct functional zones**, designed to meet the diverse needs of its residents while remaining integrated with

the surrounding neighbourhood. Importantly, residents of one block will have access to adjacent blocks' public and semi-public areas, promoting efficient land use and enhancing the overall attractiveness of the complex. For example:

- One block may feature a **multi-functional sports court**, appealing to residents who lead active lifestyles and consider proximity to sports infrastructure a major advantage.
- Another block may include a **safe, well-equipped playground** combined with recreational zones for parents and children, catering to families with young children.
- A third block may prioritise **quiet recreational spaces** for adults, including a landscaped square, benches, swings, and designated picnic areas.

This approach will help attract distinct target groups to each zone, while also fostering a cohesive community. Residents with similar interests and lifestyles will naturally gravitate toward the same areas, encouraging neighbourly relationships and social cohesion. At the same time, the **interconnected layout** allows for interaction among residents of different blocks, enriching the social and recreational life of the community through shared spaces and diverse leisure opportunities.

The competitive advantages of the residential complex will include:

- A unified architectural style across the estate (minimalism).
- A variety of housing types: detached houses, townhouses, and low-rise apartment blocks.
- Free, accessible car parks.
- Two kindergartens and one school integrated into the neighbourhood.
- Clear functional zoning within each block.
- An accessibility zone system for safety and privacy.
- Open rooftops with the potential for landscaping use.
- High-quality landscaping throughout the area.
- Exclusive pedestrian streets within residential zones.

The residential project is designed to remain within regulatory development density standards. The development coefficient for the LP is low – estimated at 20-30% of the total area – ensuring that ample space is preserved for courtyards and public areas, providing residents with a well-planned and livable environment, and creating a thriving neighbourhood culture.

The project focuses exclusively on the sale of residential real estate. However, ground-floor premises in apartment buildings or townhouses may be converted into commercial spaces by the owners through changing the designated use of these premises to non-residential.

Potential competitors for this project include gated communities, cottage settlements, and micro-districts with low-rise buildings located within the Sysertsky Urban District and adjacent areas of Yekaterinburg, offering economy- or comfort-class housing. It is important to consider residential developments in close proximity to the study area.

As previously mentioned, within Patrushi village (Sysertsky District), the *Chistye Prudy* housing estate has been commissioned. This complex comprises eight low-rise residential buildings with a secure, landscaped environment and provides comfortable living conditions for residents, including a closed territory with fencing, its own power substation, an artesian well, an automated boiler house, aerobic treatment facilities, landscaping, walking alleys, a spacious parking lot, equipped playgrounds, sports facilities, and recreational areas with gazebos [21; 22].

Thus, it can be concluded that there is a lack of residential complexes of the comfort level in the immediate vicinity of the study site. Moreover, the available residential complexes do not have the necessary social infrastructure. The *Strizhi* residential complex, located 1.7 km from the study site in the nearby town of Aramil, consists of two detached 4–5-storey, three-section buildings comprising 170 apartments ranging from 30 to 90 square metres. The complex includes an open parking lot with 61 spaces [23].

This analysis leads to the conclusion that there is a significant shortage of comfort-class residential complexes in the immediate vicinity of the study area. Furthermore, existing residential developments generally lack sufficient social infrastructure.

Several calculations have been undertaken to assess the economic feasibility of the proposed comfort-class residential project. The estimated total floor area of residential buildings is 222,500 square metres. In addition, the usable area includes land allocated for communications infrastructure, covering 182,000 square metres. The total estimated project cost is 13.8 billion roubles. The construction timeline is projected to span 19 quarters (6 years and 9 months), encompassing the completion of all buildings, utility installation, and site improvement works. The project's financial model relies on the investor's own capital [23]. The discount rate, adjusted for inflation and calculated individually using the cumulative construction method, was determined to be 8.4% [23]. Table 1 presents a summary of the project's commercial effectiveness.

Table 1

Project's commercial performance indicators

Index	Value	Unit of measure
Discount rate	8.4	%
NPV (net present value)	360 283 622	rubles
IRR (internal rate of return)	13.6	%
RI (Return on investment index)	102.6	%
Simple payback period	2 years and 10 months	-
Discounted payback period	3 years and 3 months.	-

Figure 2 shows the financial profile of the project to assess its commercial viability.

Figure 2 Financial profile of the project to assess commercial viability, RUB million/year

The proposed site revitalisation project demonstrates effectiveness due to its short payback period and strong commercial viability.

CONCLUSION

The article presents an integrated development project covering 643,000 square metres in Patrushi village, Sverdlovsk Oblast, aiming to address the revitalisation of a depressed territory. The project involves constructing affordable and comfortable housing based on the concept of integrated territorial development, which considers both the current and future urban planning context of Patrushi village and its adjacent public spaces. The development is expected to attract investment, create new jobs, and provide modern, comfortable housing for residents. Its key

distinguishing feature is the creation of a neighbourhood environment designed to appeal to diverse groups of homebuyers. In synergy with the nearby residential complex, this project will contribute to the transformation of Patrushi village and its surroundings, serving as a catalyst for converting depressed areas into attractive, contemporary living spaces.

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